

BANDITRY, KIDNAPPING, TERRORISM AND INSURGENCY IN NIGER STATE: SOCIAL AND CULTURAL REFORMS AS NON-KINETICS ALTERNATIVE

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Abstract

Scholars and the general public posit that banditry, kidnapping and insurgency as emanated in complex societies are social condition in cosmopolitan state, such as Niger state is what modern era brought, in its wake. Insurgency is inevitable and it is part of the fabrics of the nation. What the nation should strive for is regulation of crisis as part of social cankerworms or its amicable settlement whenever it arises. Since the extinction of security crisis seems impossible, all the nation needed is reform that will serve as a means for security crisis management and control. Security crisis is inevitable because it can originate in individual and group reactions to situations of scarce recourses, to division of functions within society and differentiation of power and resultant competition for scarce supplies of goods. The objectives of this study are to discuss war against insurgency and Niger state security, having social and cultural reforms as non-kinetics alternative. It is needless to mention that the world struggle and sometimes cope with this cankerworm called insurgency and terrorism. Since security crisis is a reality of human existence and therefore a means of understanding social behaviour. Thus, in this study, social and cultural reforms are recommended as a non-kinetics alternative for winning war against insurgency in Niger State. Besides its documentation, provocation of further researches and referential value to security and historical documentation, with the conscious use of primary and secondary materials which historians are noted for and the application of analyses, synthesis and correlations. To interrogate social and cultural reforms as a mechanism for security and tranquillity; historical methodology of content analysis was adopted. The conclusion provides a better insight to policy makers, political leaders, prospective investors, tourist, and migrants among others.

Keywords: Banditry, kidnapping, insurgency, terrorism, non-kinetics, culture, reforms

Introduction

Insecurity in any form would retard the developmental process of any society. This study among other aspects of life, focused on the issues of violence against farmers, as farming is a mainstay of the people in Niger state. Any form of violence that leads to insecurity is bound to affect food security, farming practices and underdevelopment anywhere in the world. The farming system is an integrated set of activities that farmers execute under their resources and circumstances to maximize productivity and net farm income sustainably. Farming system is an approach for developing farm-household systems, built on the principles of productivity, profitability, stability and sustainability. The farming system approach emphasizes understanding farm-household, community interlink age, reviews constraints and assesses potentials. However, the increased rise of banditry attacks on farming communities by the herdsmen has become an issue of economic concern.¹

Banditry, terrorism, insurgency and kidnapping are acts of robbery and violence in areas where the rule of law has broken down. Banditry consists of the organization of armed bands for the purpose of attacking state or social institutions or enterprises or individual persons. Participation in such bands and in attacks committed by them is equally regarded as banditry. In West Africa, the prevalence and severity of banditry has contributed to the rising increase in regional insecurity with a potential threat to regional integration of the sub-region.² This work

¹ Yusuf Alhassan Abdul. Effect of herdsmen and farmers conflict on food security in North Central Nigeria. Federal University, Dutsin-Ma Katsina state, Nigeria. 2020

² Collins Harper. *Social Banditry* 3rd edition, United Kingdom: Harper Collins Publishers. Retrieved from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/banditry>

made an analysis of the issues of insecurity in Niger State and suggested a non-kinetic approach to curbing it.

Geographical history and ethnic groups in Niger State

Niger State, was created by the military regime led by General Obasanjo in 1976. The area was carved out of the defunct North-Western State of Nigeria, inhabited by numerous ethnic group and has three major and most populated ethnic groups, Nupe, Hausa and Gbagyi.³ Its population according to the report of the 2006 general census was 3,950,249, which stood as the second most populated in the present day 'North Central zone after the food basket state of Benue.⁴ Niger state has twenty five local government area councils; with eight emirates for the administrative convenience of the long-standing traditional political system.⁵ These emirates include Agaie, Bida, Lapai, as these three are predominantly Nupe; Borgu, Kagara, and Kontagora, which are also predominantly Hausa; while Suleja and Minna emirates are predominantly Gbagyi. The population dominated by these three ethnic groups are in the ratio 40:32:28, making it a force to be reckoned with when it comes to politicking and numerical strengths which pose a political threat to other minority groups.⁶

Conceptual Clarification

Insurgency

The British Army Doctrine Publication on operations, defines insurgency as “the actions of a minority group within a state intent on forcing political change by means of a mixture of subversion, propaganda and military pressure, aiming to persuade or intimidate the broad mass of the people to accept such change. The goals of insurgents may be diverse, but it is simply an organized armed political struggle”.⁷ Insurgency simply connotes that someone or a group, which could be ethnic, tribal, religious or political based from within or outside the country is not happy and want a change resulting ultimately in a different political system or independence from the main group. This small group has resorted to the use of force to effect its desired change. The objectives are the people, change in the structure of the system and politics. Insurgents will resort to intimidation and violence to achieve their objective, thus the use of terror as a strategy. This has been fuelled in recent times by the rise of ethnic nationalism and religious extremism. The four stages of insurgency are; intimidation phase, terrorism phase, open confrontation against security agencies phase and consolidation phase.⁸

Terrorism

³ Raji Udo, “Disintegration of Nucleated Settlement in Northern Niger state”, *Geographical Review*, vol.1 .No.1. 1965

⁴ Abdul-Majeed Alkali, “A Retrospective Analysis of the Creation of Niger state”, in Terhamba Wuam and Mohammed Lawal Salahu (Eds), *Aspects of Niger State History- Essays in Honour of Professor Ibrahim Adamu Kolo*, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria, 2014

⁵ Ziri. R.B. “The history of Bida Emirate in the twentieth century: a study in colonialism and transformation of the social classes 1900-1960.” M.A. Thesis, History Department, Ahmadu Bello University. Zaria, 1991

⁶ Ziri. R.B. “The history of Bida Emirate in the twentieth century: a study in colonialism and transformation of the social classes 1900-1960.” M.A. Thesis, History Department, Ahmadu Bello University. Zaria, 1991

⁷ Imrana Buba, 'Bandits in Nigeria: How Protection Payments to Militias Escalate Conflict in the North West; The Conversation, 15 August 2023

⁸ Wahab, G.A. “Insurgency Terrorism and Banditry in Nigeria: Challenge to Food Security”, *Symposium*, Department of History and International Studies, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria, September 2023

Terrorism is simply the threat, use and spread of violence and the use of fear. Terrorism is coined from the French word *terrier* meaning fear. It has a long history and is an old tool used even by states against their own citizens. The Emperors, Tiberius and Caligula used it against their citizens, the Romans. Africa is not immune as struggle for independence was replete with activities the colonialists viewed as terrorism. It feeds essentially on fear and media coverage. Attempts have been made by the developed world and the UN to separate domestic and transnational terrorism, which may not always be clear or distinct. It should be noted that it is possible for an act of terrorism to take place without being insurgency motivated. Four waves of terrorism have been identified globally which are; Anarchist, Anti-colonial wave, and the current ethno-religious wave. Some scholars have also identified 3 stages of terrorism; pre-modern from civilization to July 1948 when Israel was created, the post-Israel from 1948 to 11 September 2001 and Phase 3, which is the post 2001.⁹

Banditry

Banditry refers to a form of organised or semi-organised criminal activity in which a group of individuals, labelled as bandits or outlaws, engage in acts of robbery, violence, and other criminal actions, often in rural or remote areas and communities. Bandits typically operate outside the law and often use force or the threat of force to achieve their objectives, this is akin to terrorism. Banditry is characterized by its multifaceted nature involving distinct elements. This form of criminal activity prominently features robbery and theft, where bandits target individuals, travellers and even entire communities, depriving them of their valuable possessions, livestock, and essential resources. Additionally, violence and intimidation are frequently employed tactics, as bandits use physical harm or the threat of violence to instil fear and facilitate their objectives. Again, like terrorism banditry was not seen at the inception of its development as a bad concept. In Brazil as far back as 1834 there were bandits known as *Cangaco* who were peasants operating in the North East part of the country with the support of the poor masses against the rich few. *Cangaco* or *Canga ceiro* were seen as good people who were taking resources for living from the rich to feed the poor. Banditry predominantly takes root in rural or remote areas or communities, but could also be experienced in urban centres where the presence of law enforcement is often limited or absent, providing a conducive environment for such operations. Bandits operate as organised groups, with clear leadership structures, hierarchies, and well-defined roles which enables them to execute and coordinate their criminal activities efficiently.¹⁰

Social and cultural structure of the area

Since government is borne out of society needs for orderliness and peace, in turn government could be said to be a social institution.¹¹ Every emirate in the area is headed by an Emir (or “Etsu” in the case of the three emirates of the Nupe people). The appointment of the Etsu and Emir is by the state government and is except otherwise always a lifetime appointment, as kingmakers of each emirate make recommendation and nomination for the emirate Councils for

⁹ Wahab, G.A. “Insurgency Terrorism and Banditry in Nigeria: Challenge to Food Security”, *Symposium*, Department of History and International Studies, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria, September 2023

¹⁰ Wahab, G.A. “Insurgency Terrorism and Banditry in Nigeria: Challenge to Food Security”, *Symposium*, Department of History and International Studies, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria, September 2023

¹¹ Strauss, L. & Cropsey, J. (Eds.), *History of Political Philosophy*. Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2012

the government.¹² These emirates, are carefully stated and dictated by the Islamic tenent, just as most the emirates traced their lineages and political origin to the Sokoto Caliphate before it was conquered by the British army.¹³ Today's Etsu Nupe (or Emir) of Bida, for example, is a descendant of Mallam Dendo, who won the Nupe kingdom for the Caliphate. He is a first-class emir, as are the Etsu Agaie, the Etsu Lapai, the Emir of Kontagora, the Sakin-Zazzau/Emir of Suleja, and the Emir of Minna. The other two emirs are of the second class, indicating the relative ages and strength of their domains. Although several of the emirates belong to nominally Fulani clans (as in the case of Bida), through intermarriage they have all been much "indigenized",¹⁴ so the Emir of Bida/Etsu Nupe is distinctly Nupe today. Who appears to have lost his Fulani identity. Below the emirs are lower ranks of traditional rulers, from District Heads down to Ward and Village Heads, often with their own titles derived from local ethnic traditions. They may or may not be Muslims, but most are, except perhaps among the Gbagyi, as the population of the state is predominantly Muslim as we have seen.¹⁵

The 1963 Nigerian census gave the percentages of Muslims, Christians, and "Other Religions" in what is now Niger State as 59%, 3.6%, and 37.5% respectively.¹⁶ Since 1963 most of the "Others" have become either Muslims or Christians. No census since 1963 has gathered information on religious affiliation. Majority of Muslims in Niger State, regardless of their ethnic background, are Sunni in faith and practice. Niger State now has the presence of other divisions of Muslims including Shia, Izala, Ahmadiyya or Qur'aniyyun.¹⁷

Cultural activities as reflected in religion and belief system as demonstrated a might to dictating the other aspect of humans' social life. The belief system dictates people's taboo, marriage vows, Festivals, education and other social institutions and structures.¹⁸ This has informed the discussion of the religion among the people of Niger State and the choices of their denominations.

Sufis and anti-Sufis

The main divisions of Muslims in Niger State are between the *tariqa* (Sufi) and the Izala (anti-Sufi) groups. These two Muslim religious groups are found among all the three main ethnic groups in Niger State. However there evidently appear to be more *tariqa* Muslims than the Izala

¹² Idris Abubakar Zakari, "The Socio-Cultural Ceremonies amongst the Gbagyi in Minna in the Nineteenth Century" in Terhemba Wuam and Mohammed Lawal Salahu (Eds), *Aspects of Niger State History- Essays in Honour of Professor Ibrahim Adamu Kolo*, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria, 2014

¹³ Jimada. S.I. "The establishment of Patigi Emirate: the historical background c1810-1898" M.A Thesis, History Department. Ahmadu Bello University. Zaria, 1992

¹⁴ Jimada. S.I. "The establishment of Patigi Emirate: the historical background c1810-1898" M.A Thesis, History Department. Ahmadu Bello University. Zaria.1992

¹⁵ Idrees, A.A.. "Gogo Habiba of Bida the rise and demise of a nineteenth century, Nupe merchant princess and politician" African study monographs 12(1) 1991

¹⁶ Muhammad Umaru Ndagi, "Muslims of Niger State: A Survey", *Nigeria Research Network* (NRN) Oxford Department of International Development, Queen Elizabeth House, University of Oxford, background paper no. 6, January 2012

¹⁷ Muhammad Umaru Ndagi, "Muslims of Niger State: A Survey", *Nigeria Research Network* (NRN) Oxford Department of International Development, Queen Elizabeth House, University of Oxford, background paper no. 6, January 2012

¹⁸ Dawood O.Egbefo and ABE, Olajide Mayowa, Traditional Festivals among the Benin People of Edo State Nigeria as Instruments of Intra-Inter-group Relations: Lesson for Nigeria, *Perspectives in History, Development and International Relations: Festschrift for Professor Ibrahim James*, Terhemba Wuam and Philibus A. Nwamagyi (eds), Department of History Kaduna State University, Kaduna, 2018

among the Nupe. There also appears to be more Izala followers among the Hausa than can be found among Nupe and Gwari Muslims in Niger State. Beyond these generalizations it is impossible to be more precise about percentages.¹⁹ The relationship between the *tariqa* and Izala groups in Niger state is very cordial and peaceful. No violence has been witnessed or reported among them in the State, at least, in the past three decades.

Tijaniyya and Qadiriyya

Among the Sufis, as in many other states in northern Nigeria, most by far are adherents of the Tijaniyya order; only an insignificant number are followers of Qadiriyya. Thus, we could say while the Tijaniyya represent about 95% of Sufis, Qadiriyya are about 5%.²⁰ There are no class distinctions in the followerships of Sufi orders in Niger State: their followers can be found among all classes.

Neither Sufi nor anti-Sufi

Similarly, there are Muslims among the three main ethnic groups in Niger State who are neither *tariqa* nor Izala. Only about 20% of the Muslims in Niger State can be said to belong to this category. However, most Nupe Muslims are followers of the *tariqa* in the same way that many Hausa Muslims in the state are followers of the Izala sect. Significant numbers of Gbagyi Muslims in Niger State are neither *tariqa* nor Izala.²¹

Darul Islam

There existed before now a Muslim community called Darul Islam (meaning “Land of Islam”) in Mokwa Local Government Area of the state. This community was disbanded in 2009 following the insurgence of religious crisis caused by Boko Haram in Borno and other states. Residents of the Darul Islam community were returned at government expense to their indigenous places of birth mostly in Kano, Jigawa and Zamfara States.²² There were few others whose origins were traced to towns in the neighbouring Niger Republic.

The People and Christianity

Christians among the people (indigene) of Niger State are of little percentage covering significantly Muyan, Doko, Gwadafu as other areas have non-indigene migrants spread across the areas. The extension of Christian Missionaries to Niger State was as a result of the Christian Missionary’s activities of Samuel Ajayi Crowther who achieved his Mission by establishing two stations and set the pace for the incursion of Christianity into the Nupeland. Gbagyi areas and the rest areas of the Niger State.²³

¹⁹ Muhammad Umaru Ndagi, “Muslims of Niger State: A Survey”, *Nigeria Research Network* (NRN) Oxford Department of International Development, Queen Elizabeth House, University of Oxford, background paper no. 6, January 2012

²⁰ Muhammad Umaru Ndagi, “Muslims of Niger State: A Survey”, *Nigeria Research Network* (NRN) Oxford Department of International Development, Queen Elizabeth House, University of Oxford, background paper no. 6, January 2012

²¹ Muhammad Umaru Ndagi, “Muslims of Niger State: A Survey”, *Nigeria Research Network* (NRN) Oxford Department of International Development, Queen Elizabeth House, University of Oxford, background paper no. 6, January 2012

²² Muhammad Umaru Ndagi, “Muslims of Niger State: A Survey”, *Nigeria Research Network* (NRN) Oxford Department of International Development, Queen Elizabeth House, University of Oxford, background paper no. 6, January 2012

²³ Usman M.T., and Zakari Aldris Abubakar, “Islamization Campaigns in the Gbagyi Areas of Former Minner Chieftdom” in Wuam Terhemba and Salahu Mohammed Lawal (Eds.), *Aspects of Niger State History: Essays in Honour of Professor Ibrahim Adamu Kolo*, IBB University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria, 2014

The genesis of the Christian religion in the area and its acceptance was as a result of the introduction of western education and the preaching about polygamy. Oral traditions reveal that the Missionaries were stationed at St. Peters Parish Bida and this aided the spread of Christianity to other area of this study.

Banditry, Insurgency, Terrorism and Kidnapping in Niger State

Niger State is one of the most hit in recent past in term of banditry, insurgency, terrorism and kidnapping activities as selected examples of such attacks may be necessary here. These bandits severely attacked forty communities between March and December of 2015. Thirty-eight persons lost their lives and several others ran away from their homes. The bandits took 300 sheep and 2,000 animals from the people. 15 further persons were abducted, and their relatives paid a ransom of almost N11 million to free them. In order to assess the trend, Dr. Muazu Babangida Aliyu, the state's governor at the time, called a stakeholder meeting right once. Attendees included the leaders of all local governments, emirs, districts, and village heads, and the *Miyetti* Allah Cattle Breeders Association, Niger State. The government was then provided with security files that shaved the individuals alleged to be responsible for the horrific murders in which the well-known herders were not among. Nonetheless, the material was allegedly buried beneath the carpet.²⁴

In 2016, 36 violent attacks were conducted in roughly 70 localities throughout the three local government areas. The Rafi Local Government Area's Pangu, Kukoki, Zara, and Kushreki communities all turned into battlegrounds. The bandits did not spare Pandogeri, Allawa, or Madaka in the same Local Government Area. In addition to 2,600 cattle being rustled, over 50 people were slain, 12 more were kidnapped, and relatives had to pay N5 million in ransom to get the victims freed. Feeling unsettled by these ceaseless murders, former senator David Umaru for the impacted zone conveyed his grievances to the Abuja Security Forces and requesting for their help. The action paid off, as Ibrahim Idris, the then-Inspector General of Police from Niger State, directed the then Muazu Zubaru, the state's commissioner of Police, Muazu Zuubairu to track down those responsible. Following this instruction, the police and their sister security services launched Operation Puff Adder, a full-scale assault on the bandits that gave these villages some respite.²⁵

But on January 15, 2017, the bandits struck once more, leaving nine people dead and render 6,000 people homeless. A N3 million ransom was eventually paid to free the five kidnapped individuals. 11 individuals were killed between April and June of 2017, and the inhabitants paid a ransom of over N30 million to obtain the return of the victims, along with about 150 sheep and 1,000 cattle that had been rustled. Twenty villages in the Kushreki community in Rafi Local Government, home to roughly 250,000 people, served as these armed men's safe haven between September and December of 2017. Six months later, the bandits in the area carried out another attack, in which they killed six individuals and kidnapped nineteen more, among whom Zara, an SS11 female student at Day Secondary School, who worked as a cook for the abducted for two weeks before her release after a ransom was paid on her behalf. After

²⁴ Muazu Babangida Aliyu, <https://www.vanguardnews.com.2015>. Accessed on 9 January 2023.

²⁵ <https://www.google.com.2016>. Accessed on 9 January 2023

selling nearly all of their agricultural produce, the communities that came together paid N11 million to guarantee the release of the remaining persons in captivities.²⁶

October 16, 2018 saw the deaths of no fewer than 13 vigilante corps members and the kidnapping of 30 more people by bandits in Niger State. The incident happened at Kuserki village in Rafi local government area of the state. It was part of a recent wave of bandit attacks on rural communities in areas of Paikoro, Rafi, Shiroro, and Munya local government areas. It was discovered that the vigilante corps was caught off guard during the nighttime attacks. According to sources, the robbers ambushed the vigilante corps members after storming the area in huge numbers on motorbikes, brandishing deadly weapons and firing indiscriminately to intimidate the inhabitants. A vigilante who escaped the assault narrated that they had confronted the bandits in a furious struggle but were defeated by their superior fire arms. Mr. Ishaya Ishaku stated that on December 16, 2018, bandits attacked their hamlet and stole all they owned, including clothes, rice, hens, beans, oil, and chickens. No one was taken from their home, but they did kidnap their neighbor's daughter.²⁷

On April 4, 2019, bandits attacked Kukoki village and killed Danasabe, the vigilante chairman of Rafi Local Government Area, in Majanjan village. His staff and the people were rescued, however (see appendix 2). A witness by the name of Mr. Haruna said that they took his phone and released him. And they kidnapped 20 people from Tashan Kare on that exact day. After the kidnapped individuals were held captive for around two months, the bandit demanded a ransom that included a Honda motorcycle, bags of rice, and three million dollars for each individual. In the same month, they carried out a nighttime attack on the Zara village, killed three people, kidnapped eight others, and released disabled person among them. And the remaining ones bandit requested for five million naira. And the next day, they kidnapped two people from the same village: Tanko's wives, Ladi and Fatima, albeit Fatima passed away during their captivity. After paying ₦500,000 with a bag of rice, a #50,000 recharge card, and 25 liters of groundnut oil, Ladi was liberated after a week. Bandit attacked Ugwan Buhari on the 29 September and did away with their cattle and property and abducted four people and three people were killed, according to the source the village was on fire that day which he happened to be an eye witness of the incident that took place.²⁸

Nine people, including three members of the Nigerian military, were allegedly killed on August 18, 2020, at Tashan Kare and Yakila towns in the Rafi local government area of Niger State as a result of an attack by gunmen. Adamu Usman, the Niger State Commissioner of Police, would not comment on the fatalities but only acknowledged to the News Agency of Nigeria that a Chinese expatriate and a Nigerian had been abducted in Yakila. According to additional information obtained by Channels Television, the attackers initially entered the Yakila village on Monday at around noon and started shooting at foreign workers and some Nigerian nationals who were repairing Minna Zungeru Road. The incident was also verified by local residents and National Orientation Agency employees Iliyasu Mohammed to Channels Television via telephone conversation. He said that after opening fire when the bandits arrived in Yakila, they pursued the foreigners and the construction workers who were working along the road. An operation to free a Chinese national and his driver who had been abducted by unknown gunmen in Yakila, Rafi local government area, Niger state, is reported to have claimed the lives of three

²⁶ <https://www.nigerianews.com> January 15, 2023. Accessed 9 January 2023

²⁷ Ishaya Ishaku age 38 years oral interview at Ungwan Buhari farmer 16 July 2023

²⁸ Haruna Garba age 40 years oral interview at Tashan Kare farmer 20 July 2023

troops and one vigilante. The story goes that the victims of a rescue attempt to free the Chinese expatriate and his chauffeur were killed in a gunfight with the armed bandits, who were reportedly numbering in the thirties. The victims were taken hostage at a construction firm in the Yakila area. Our reporter received an eyewitness account stating that the shooters entered Yakila on 15 motorbikes with passengers on the back of each bike, heavily armed.²⁹

The *Dan-Makaranta* bandit faction attacked Abdulhameed Ibrahim, the district chief of Yakila village, on December 10, 2020, and abducted him. According to a family source, Abdulhameed Ibrahim, who spoke to FIJ, the district head informed his people that terrorists were causing chaos in the nearby village of Garin Gabas. Sadly, he was taken advantage of. Along with him were a health worker named Halima and her child, as well as Ilyasu Mukhtar, a youth leader for the All Progressives Congress (APC) in Garin Gabas. According to the source, a ransom of seven million naira was negotiated for him and the other kidnapped victims from Garin Gabas. The district head received N3 million, the health worker and her child received N3 million, and the youth leader received N1 million. Within a week, the victims' family collected the ransom, and a few delegates took the money to the bandits in their hideout. He said that although the delegates had hoped to bring the abducted victims back home, it had not happened. The toddler and the health worker were the only ones released.³⁰

Additionally, on December 20, 2020, three people were reported to have been slain by bandits in the Madaka, Rafi Local Government Area of Niger State. Among them was Mallam Isyaku Alhassan, the leader of a vigilante organization. It was discovered that the attacks happened between 11:30 and 12:30. Other victims included Abdulhamid Isyaku, the vigilante's er, and an unidentified individual whose identity was yet unknown. It was also reported that the village chief of the Madaka community had been abducted by the armed bandits twice. Recall that the village chief was taken hostage during a bandit invasion and held captive for three months before being freed from their hold.³¹

The kidnapping of 52 travelers who were using public transportation on February 28, 2021, marked a recent low point in the situation in the area. In the state of April, they launch their initial attack on Kagara Town. Low cost; only one person died in the second attack. Which Kagara Town's First Bank was also attacked Three people were slain: a bank security guard, a Rafi Local Government Area employee, and security personnel. Witnesses reported that at approximately 6 p.m. on that day, a large group of armed men on motorbikes rushed the area, opening fire in the air before making their way to the bank. They also mentioned how many locals were injured by bullets, to differing degrees. Because of the uprising, the first bank is no more functioning in Rafi Local Government Area.(see appendix 3).³²

On February 28, 2021, there was another attack at the Government Science College Kagara, headquarters of Rafi Local Government Area. It was also reported that some instructors and their families who were staying in the College Staff Quarters had been kidnapped by the gunman. Benjamin Doma was the deceased student, and the attackers appeared to have planned their attack because they were wearing the school uniform. The attackers reportedly broke inside

²⁹ Ibrahim Yusuf, age: 30, *Facebook* interview, 20 July 2023

³⁰ <https://www.channelstv.com/2020/08/18>.via phone conversation. Accessed on 8 August 2023

³¹ <https://www.channelstv.com/2020/08/18>. Accessed on 8 August 2023

³² Julian Moses, age: 40, oral interview at Kagara, Rafi Local Government Area, 16 August 2023

Government Science College Kagara at around 2:00 am and began shooting intermittently, according to the source. A student lost their life in the process, while several more were shot. Additionally, a few College employees and their families were kidnapped from their houses. The number of people kidnapped and injured as of the report's filing, however, was not disclosed by the source. The report claims that as a result of the conflict, Tegna's Government Secondary School and Government Science Colleges were closed. Tuesday saw gunmen attack Monday Kuryas' palace in Rafi Local Government Area Kagara. In a statement released at night, the State Commissioner of Police stated that at approximately 5:30 p.m., the bandits carrying lethal weapons entered the Emir's palace and the local divisional police headquarters. He claimed that during the event, two people and a policeman were shot and killed.³³

On April 3, 2021, there was another attack on Ungwan Tanko village. Four people were taken hostage: two married ladies, Safiya and Azumi Mohammed; a boy, Anas Mohammed; and Mohammed himself. The four individuals were liberated after a ransom of four million naira was paid. Mr. Mohammed Tegna, a victim of the crime, stated that his neighbor's daughter was also kidnapped, and he testified about the suffering and anguish they endured at the hands of the bandit. The wives of Alhaji Bala and Alhaji Mota were also kidnapped in May 2021, and a ransom of two million naira was demanded. Attack Tashan Kura as well, get rid of the cows, and destroy their rooms and parked the clothes of Mrs Bala Dantani. Islammiyya students were abducted in the same month. The kidnapping occurred on May 30th, 2021 just after bandits reportedly opened fire on Tegna people, scaring off bystanders. A total of 200 people, including 136 students and their teachers, were abducted from the school. After a few weeks, two of the kids managed to get out of captivity. When word of the kidnapping spread, another parent's death was also confirmed. While verifying the students' release, the owner of the school stated that the kids were currently en route to Minna, where they will be picked up by the state government. Following the kidnapping, the bandits first sought N300 million as ransom; however, they then lowered their demand to ₦50 million, which was paid in two installments. Before releasing the kids, who had been detained for 88 days, or three months, the kidnappers insisted on receiving an additional N20 million and six motorcycles in addition to the ₦50 million ransoms.³⁴ (See appendix 5)

A group of people, including Victoria Ayuba, Amos Ayuba, Yohanna Ayuba, Paulina Amos, Bilha Philip, James Philip, Mrs. Sunday, and several others, were abducted by them in January 2022 when they broke into Tashan Kura. The abductors demanded a ransom of 11 million naira, which was paid to the bandit before the victims could be freed. In the same month, they kidnapped ten people in Tashan Bako and demanded a ransom of five million naira to release them. They also demanded a ransom of seven million naira to release the ten people who had been taken. The source claimed that several properties were destroyed, communities were on fire, and some individuals were hurt. The kidnappees thank God for saving them and setting them free.³⁵

In June 2023, a serious attack occurred in Gimi. It happened on a Friday at 11 p.m., while everyone was sleeping and enjoying their night off. Bandits broke in and took 13 people, but one managed to escape, leaving 12 people with the bandit. The town was completely destroyed, and many items were lost. After the ransom of eleven million naira was paid, a woman returned

³³ Inusa Kabiru, age: 45, oral interview at Kagara, Rafi Local Government open Registry 16 August 2023

³⁴ Mohammed Tegna, age: 50, farmer, oral interview at Tegna, 17 August 2023

³⁵ Yohanna Ayuba, age: 41, farmer oral interview at Tashan kura, 20 August 2023

carrying a pregnancy. The victims, who included Alhaji Bello, Mai Dabo, Duruwanu, Sale Haruna, Yahaya, and others, were returned in August. The same week, they also abducted five individuals from Katako and killed a lady and two married ladies who were with their animals.³⁶

On August 24, 2023, bandits are said to have assaulted Garin Gabas near Kagara in the Rafi Local Government Area of Niger state, gravely injuring two mobile police officers. In addition, the robbers destroyed many homes and set fire to two of the security personnel's vehicles. A source from the area said that the bandits also rustled a large number of cattle and abducted an unknown number of persons. Information had it that a large group of bandits were traveling through the neighbourhood to target another town. However, the security personnel spotted them and pursued them briskly, leading to a violent gunfight between the assailants and the agents.³⁷

No fewer than 13 soldiers were killed by bandits in Niger state on the attack of July 2023. The military also lost helicopter during the evacuation of the casualties. The incident occurred around Kundu in the Rafi local government area near Zungeru town of Niger State. It was gathered that not less than 10 other security men were injured in the deadly attack with the bandits. It was also gathered that about 50 bandits were killed in the encounter with their bodies left in the forest while those that were injured were ferried away by members of their gang. It was further gathered that a military helicopter was used to convey the dead to the General Hospital, Zingeru before a vehicle came Monday morning to evacuate the corpses to unknown destination. The military has however confirmed that a helicopter on evacuation mission crashed Monday in Niger State. A statement issued by the Spokesman of the Nigerian Air Force, Air Commodore Edward Gabkwet, said the aircraft crashed in Chukuba Village in Niger State.³⁸

Causes and Effects of Banditry, Insurgency, Terrorism and Kidnapping in Niger State

Poverty as a social cankerworm

Niger State could be regarded as poor when looking at the index of standard of living in the area. The State, with its huge human and material resources have more than 70 percent of its population living on poverty line. The situation is such that the area is seen as a rich in alluvia soil for viable agriculture yet the State struggle to feed her population as a result of bandits activities mostly around Shiroro, Kagara, Muyan, Kuta, Rafi and Kontogora areas. The poverty challenge has contributed to the spate of insurgency, terrorism and banditry, with a debilitating consequence for food security as being experienced nationwide. This, in turn is forcing the people to provide support and become a ready source of recruitment into criminal groups.³⁹

Marginalisation and nepotism

Since independence in 1960, the issue of marginalisation and nepotism have been recurring vocabularies in the nation's dictionary. These two issues contributed significantly to the eruption of the Civil War from 1967 to 1970, the scar of which is the IPOB of today. In any society once a group feels marginalised, it moves to the periphery to be part of the opposition to challenge the

³⁶ Audu Yohanna, age: 46, farmer, oral interview at Gimi, 20 August 2023

³⁷ www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2023/07/24 accessed on the 8 August 2023

³⁸ www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2023/07/24 accessed on the 8 August 2023

³⁹ Wafulu Okumu and Anneli Botha, 'Domestic Terrorism in Africa; Understanding, Addressing its impact on Human Security; Institute for Security Studies, South Africa November 2007

system and create problems for the larger society. The Niger Delta militants and IPOB separatists are examples of this assertion.⁴⁰ The struggle for dominant among the three major groups in Niger state has generated heat and most time unhealthy politics in the state.

Religious and ethnic crisis

Niger State like other countries in the Sahel Region is a melting point of Islam and Arab traditions and Christianity in the area. African communities have learned nothing from their histories and forgotten everything about atrocities committed against them by others. Nigerians have failed to learn from the occurrences or even forget about centuries old wars and conquests, which actually fuelled and assisted slave trade. This ravaged Africa for more than 300 years, depriving the Continent particularly sub-Sahara Africa of human resources required for development.⁴¹ Niger State accommodated not just Muslim and Christians, but also adherents of African religion. This has always been a factor of insecurity among the people.

Lack of social justice and inequality

Drawing directly from the religious and ethnic intolerance is the problem of social injustice and inequality. This is fuelled by the ‘Zero Sum’ politics practiced in Nigeria at large, which gives the winner complete control of state resources, thereby propagating discrimination and marginalisation amongst the different groups and people.⁴²

Porous borders

Borders of all African countries including Nigeria are porous, open and lacking essential monitoring devices, which has facilitated the trafficking in drugs, weapons and humans across the continent. Nigeria’s border with Benin is 773km, Cameroun 1,690km, Chad 87km and Niger Republic is 1,497km all porous, with more than one thousand illegal crossing points making movement of insurgents, terrorists, bandits and criminals easy in and out of the country.⁴³

Social and cultural policies as a mechanism for security

Osaro, , observed that one of the themes of the new thinking is the idea that security policy should have social accommodation as a primary and persistent aim. He further advocates for the emancipation of the individual. To him emancipation means.

*Freeing people from those constraints that stop them from carrying out what freely they would choose to do of which war, poverty, oppression and poor education are a few... it is emancipation, not power and order, in theory and practice that leads to stable security.*⁴⁴

⁴⁰ Wahab, G.A. “Insurgency Terrorism and Banditry in Nigeria: Challenge to Food Security”, *Symposium*, Department of History and International Studies, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria, September 2023

⁴¹ Richard I. Somiari, “Forensics and National Security”: Possibilities and Challenges; in *Issues of Terrorism, Insurgency and Security in Nigeria* (GA Wahab and CBN Ogbogbo edn.) Nigerian Army Resource Centre, Abuja, 2020

⁴² Richard I. Somiari, “Forensics and National Security”: Possibilities and Challenges; in *Issues of Terrorism, Insurgency and Security in Nigeria* (GA Wahab and CBN Ogbogbo edn.) Nigerian Army Resource Centre, Abuja, 2020

⁴³ Imrana Buba, “Bandits in Nigeria”: How Protection Payments to Militias Escalate Conflict in the North West; *The Conversation* 15 August 2023

⁴⁴ Osaro, G.E *The Meaning of Nigerian History*, Ibadan University Press, Ibadan University Press, Ibadan, 1989

Osaro posited that threats to national security can manifest in social form.⁴⁵ Nwakanma again warns that coercive force alone cannot guarantee national security especially in situation of structural injustice and endemic poverty as is reflected in Niger state.⁴⁶

Thirdly, some of the measures adopted to promote accommodation of differences and “unity in diversity” have had the unfortunate effect of increasing differences in at the state level as we have in Niger state. Such measures include the creation of new states and local government, introduction of “federal character principle”, in Nigeria constitution. All of these are enshrined in the Nigerian constitution. Although these measures are meant to moderate the divisive effect of ethnic and regional competition for power and opportunity, the manner in which they have been implemented has heightened ethnicity and ill feelings among the various ethnic groups in Niger state.⁴⁷

There is also the problem of diminishing resources and the Nigerian economic crisis as reflected in Niger State. The Nigerian economic crisis and the harsh economic realities which have heightened the level of anxiety, fear and uncertainty have negatively impacted on ethnic identity as individual and groups tend to be less tolerant and more prone to violence. And those in public offices loot the national treasury in reckless abandon. Again there is the failure of the state to perform its routine services to the people that have led to its loss of legitimacy. And because the state increasingly came to be seen as incapable of promoting the general interests as opposed to sectional interests (ethnic and religious interests), and yet very repressive and authoritarian, people naturally rallied around ethnic identities especially as a form of coping mechanism.⁴⁸

Making a case out of the issues of social and cultural redundancy, Chamba admits that, it was to ensure peaceful co-existence of various ethnic groups in the polity, that the people and the government chose the adopting restructuring social institutions. Unfortunately, its implementation continues to pose serious problem to the political cohesion as a result of some obvious problems. And as a way forward, Chamba suggested that: societies must change their basic social structures for peaceful co-existence, and there must be equitable distribution of resources and balance of power that will take into cognizance the interests of the minority, eradicate corruption as a social cankerworm, and the incorporation of good governance in the nation’s democracy indicating a fine social and organized society.⁴⁹

Understanding depravity as factor for insurgency, terrorism and banditry

The moralists consider depravity ‘as an immoral and unethical phenomenon that contains a set of moral aberrations from moral standards of society. Causing loss of respect for and confidence in duly constituted authorities’.⁵⁰ A prominent proponent of this view is Nye; defines depravity as:

⁴⁵ Osaro, G.E *The Meaning of Nigerian History*, Ibadan University Press, Ibadan University Press, Ibadan, 1989

⁴⁶ Nwakanma, O., *Social Security is National Security*. *Sunday Vanguard*, August 12, p.16

⁴⁷ ABE Olajide Mayowa, Salahu Mohammed Lawal and Ilyasu Yakubu Ahmed, Interrogating Religion as a Factor of Integration in Lapai, 1976-2019, *DIYA 'U Journal of History and International Studies (DJHIS)*, , Federal University, Bernin Kebbi, Vol.2, Issue 1, 2024

⁴⁸ Adams, O. *Ethnicity, Nationalism and Federalism in Nigeria*, Warri Coastal Academy Books, 2009

⁴⁹ Chamba, M. “The Effects of Ethnicity, Corruption and Good Governance in Nigeria *THISDAY* Vol.11, No.5423, 6 September, 2006. p.23

⁵⁰ ABE, Olajide Mayowa, *et al*, “Depravity And Its Consequences On Nigeria’s Aspiration Towards Nation Building” *Lapai Journal of Nigerian History*, Vol. 12, No. 1, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, 2020

A behavior that deviates from the formal duties of a public role (elective or appointive) because of private regarding (personal, close family, private clique) wealth or status gains, or violates rules against the exercise of certain types of private-regarding influence.⁵¹

The moralist view is circulated on the basis that it can tend to individualise a societal phenomenon and attempts to dichotomise as to what is good and what is bad. In the process, societal contexts are ignored and the gap between formal norms and the underlying practice-gird norms are abandoned as the case in Niger State.⁵²

The slogan of Nigerians has now become “everyone is corrupt”; so, is a legal participation and the few non-participants are victimized. The menace of depravity has been responsible for the vicious cycle of failed political leadership, political instability, economic mismanagement and underdevelopment, social chaos, disintegrative tendencies and subversive action. This fact becomes most poignant when viewed against the persistence of the phenomenon. As far back as the 1970s the late Chief Obafemi Awolowo, a frontline nationalist and former Premier of the South-West Region observed that:

Since independence, Nigerian governments have been a matter of few holding the cow for the strongest and most cunning to milk. Under those circumstances everybody runs over everybody to make good at the expense of others.⁵³

The above opinion of late Chief Obafemi Awolowo tells us why there would not be development until “we kill depravity” just as late Rueben Zhiri opined that: “if we fail to kill capitalism; one day capitalism will humanity”.⁵⁴ If we fail to kill depravity; one day depravity will kill humanity.

Conclusion

The confrontation of Niger State area indigenous culture with a foreign culture was largely through religion, trade and politics with implication of insurgency, terrorism, banditry and kidnapping. This ‘attack’ on the primordial value transformed to a normal complex challenge of a modern society with careless approach to modernization that had resulted to what seems to be an ‘endless’ crisis of insecurity in the area. The non-kinetic approach to solving this quagmire is social and cultural re-oriental as social and cultural reforms would reconfigure the minds of people and change the basic structures and system of the society to naturally object and regard such menace as abnormal and unacceptable in the society.

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⁵² Turaki, Y. *The British Colonial Legacy in Northern Nigeria: A Social Ethical Analysis of the Colonial and Post-Colonial Society and Politics in Nigeria*. Arewa House. 1993

⁵³ See, ABE, Olajide Mayowa, *et al*, “Depravity And Its Consequences On Nigeria’s Aspiration Towards Nation Building” *Lapai Journal of Nigerian History*, Vol. 12, No. 1, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, Niger State, 2020

⁵⁴ Oral Interview, Rueben Zhiri, age: 49, History Lecturer, Ibrahim Badamasi Babngida University, Lapai, Niger State, Nigeria

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